

IRREVERSIBLE ELECTROPORATION (IRE) FOR THE TREATMENT OF PEDIATRIC ADENOTONSILLAR HYPERTROPHY: PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Khasanov U.S.

Khudayberganov U.R.

Tashkent State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19436378>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 22nd March 2026

Accepted: 26th March 2026

Online: 31st March 2026

KEYWORDS

Although these less invasive procedures have demonstrated some benefits, reductions in postoperative pain and bleeding have been only modest

ABSTRACT

Tonsillectomy is a common surgical procedure in children, most often indicated for upper airway obstruction or recurrent infections. In 2019, an estimated 559,900 ambulatory and 7,100 inpatient tonsillectomies were performed in the United States. In recent years, various techniques and technologies have been developed to reduce complications such as pain and bleeding, including intracapsular approaches using coblation or the microdebrider.

Tonsillectomy is a common surgical procedure in children, most often indicated for upper airway obstruction or recurrent infections. In 2019, an estimated 559,900 ambulatory and 7,100 inpatient tonsillectomies were performed in the United States. In recent years, various techniques and technologies have been developed to reduce complications such as pain and bleeding, including intracapsular approaches using coblation or the microdebrider. Although these less invasive procedures have demonstrated some benefits, reductions in postoperative pain and bleeding have been only modest. Electroporation involves the application of pulsed electrical fields to tissue, resulting in the disruption of cellular ion channels. At higher energy levels, pore formation becomes irreversible, inducing cellular apoptosis and subsequent tissue ablation. A key advantage of this technique is the precise application of electrical fields, which minimizes damage to surrounding tissue and reduces the risk of complications. Furthermore, the non-thermal nature of the procedure may help alleviate postoperative pain. The electrical pulses, typically delivered within microsecond durations, also allow for shorter procedure times. Irreversible electroporation (IRE) is increasingly being used for ablation in conditions such as liver cancer, cardiac arrhythmias, and prostate cancer. Recently, we have shown the efficacy and safety of this technique for tonsillar ablation in a cohort of adults. IRE provides a non-thermal alternative to traditional ablation methods, further decreasing the risk of collateral damage to adjacent tissues. This preliminary study is the first to apply IRE technology for non-thermal ablation of the tonsils and adenoids in children. Irreversible electroporation (IRE) is a novel non-thermal tissue ablation technology.

The objective of this study was to evaluate the safety and efficacy of IRE in the treatment of adenotonsillar hypertrophy in children.

Methods: In this prospective, before- and-after study conducted at an academic medical center, 12 children aged 5-13 years with adenoid or adenotonsillar hypertrophy were enrolled. Eight patients underwent adenotonsillar ablation and 4 adenoid ablation. All procedures were performed under general anesthesia. IRE was applied to the tonsils and/or adenoids using the ENTire™ system. Postoperative pain was assessed daily for one week using the Wong-Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale. Quality-of-life outcomes were evaluated using the Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA-18) questionnaire and the Pediatric Sleep Questionnaire - Sleep-Related Breathing Disorder scale (PSQ-SRBD) questionnaire at baseline and 1-month post-procedure. Tonsillar size was assessed using the Brodsky grading scale.

Results: The mean procedure time was 12 minutes 15 seconds \pm 4 minutes 27 seconds, with no intraoperative or postoperative bleeding observed. Postoperative pain on day 1 ranged from 2 to 5 (mean \pm SD, 3.0 \pm 0.95) and resolved completely (score 0) in all patients by day 7. At baseline, the OSA-18 score ranged from 3.0 to 5.2 (mean \pm SD, 4.11 \pm 0.59), the PSQ-SRBD score ranged from 0.55 to 0.86 (mean \pm SD, 0.60 \pm 0.11), and the mean Brodsky grade was 3.2 \pm 0.4. At 1-month post-procedure, OSA-18 score decreased to a range of 1.0 to 1.22 (mean \pm SD, 1.04 \pm 0.07; $p < 0.001$), and the PSQ-SRBD score decreased to a range of 0.00 to 0.09 (mean \pm SD, 0.04 \pm 0.04 ; $p < 0.001$). Among the 8 patients who underwent tonsillar ablation, the Brodsky grade scale decreased to 1.3 \pm 0.5 ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion: This preliminary study is the first to evaluate IRE technology for non-thermal adenotonsillar tissue ablation in pediatric patients. The procedure was brief, associated with less postoperative pain compared to standard treatment, and was not complicated by bleeding. In the short term, tonsillar size was reduced and clinical scores of obstructive symptoms improved. Larger multicenter clinical trials with long-term follow-up are in progress.

References:

1. Ahmarani G, El Khoury P, Aoun M, Ahmarani MC, Rassi S. Recurrence of sleep apnea in children after intracapsular coblation tonsillectomy: A comprehensive exploration of tonsil regrowth. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2024 Jun;181:111992. doi: 10.1016/j.ijporl.2024.111992. Epub 2024 May 23. PMID: 38805935.
2. Kumar DS, Valenzuela D, Kozak FK, Ludemann JP, Moxham JP, Lea J, Chadha NK. The reliability of clinical tonsil size grading in children. *JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2014 Nov;140(11):1034-7. doi: 10.1001/jamaoto.2014.2338. PMID: 25317509.
3. Lee HS, Yoon HY, Jin HJ, Hwang SH. The safety and efficacy of powered intracapsular tonsillectomy in children: A meta-analysis. *Laryngoscope*. 2018 Mar;128(3):732-744. doi: 10.1002/lary.26886. Epub 2017 Oct 25. PMID: 29068049.
4. Lin H, Hajarizadeh B, Wood AJ, Selvarajah K, Ahmadi O. Postoperative Outcomes of Intracapsular Tonsillectomy With Coblation: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2024 Feb;170(2):347-358. doi: 10.1002/ohn.573. Epub 2023 Nov 8. PMID: 37937711.
5. Russo E, Festa BM, Costantino A, Bernardocchi A, Spriano G, De Virgilio A. Postoperative Morbidity of Different Tonsillectomy Techniques: A Systematic Review and Network Meta-Analysis. *Laryngoscope*. 2024 Apr;134(4):1696-1704. doi: 10.1002/lary.31116. Epub 2023 Oct 16. PMID: 37843298.

- 6.Sarafoleanu C, Tanase I, Passali D, DeRowe A. Irreversible electroporation for tonsillar ablation in adults: Oral presentation, American Academy of Otolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery, Indianapolis, Oct. 2025
- 7.Tabaja C, Younis A, Hussein AA, Taigen TL, Nakagawa H, Saliba WI, Sroubek J, Santangeli P, Wazni OM. Catheter-Based Electroporation: A Novel Technique for Catheter Ablation of Cardiac Arrhythmias. *JACC Clin Electrophysiol.* 2023 Sep;9(9):2008-2023. doi: 10.1016/j.jacep.2023.03.014. Epub 2023 Jun 21. PMID: 37354168.
- 8.Wilson YL, Merer DM, Moscatello AL. Comparison of three common tonsillectomy techniques: a prospective randomized, double-blinded clinical study. *Laryngoscope.* 2009 Jan;119(1):162-70. doi: 10.1002/lary.20024. PMID: 19117287.

